

Indigenous Elites and Social Legislations in Colonial Malabar(1792-1933)

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This article is looking at the making of three acts on customs and usages of Malabar by the colonial government. These enactments were done in three different phases of the colonial rule. So this will help us in understanding the dynamics of legal development, how the indigenous elites and interests of the state came into play at different points. Indian Slavery Act V of 1843 which was in the phase of early colonialism was a product of debates and discussions that happened in the colonial administrative sphere alone. The Malabar Marriage Act of 1896 was the result of the very first attempt of the indigenous elites and The Malabar Tenancy Act of 1930 was the further extended and developed version of that process. This section will concentrate on the way in which the legislation was brought out, what were the discussions and which spheres these discussions happened.

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The concept of 'elite' is generally understood as a category of individuals or groups with "disproportionate control or access to resources" (Khan, 2012, p. 362). Social scientists who worked on this concept have argued that the elite class is plural, since there is a decline and degeneration among them, which makes others occupy the elite position. Hence, elites are not a static category; rather, there is a "circulation of elites" in history (Pareto, 1935, p. 359). Bourdieu elaborated on the concept by identifying the various subfields in the 'field of power' (Jodhka & Naudet, 2019, p. 7). Bourdieu also discussed the state's role in legitimising and delegitimising individuals, along with contributing to the sociocultural and economic capital (Wacquant, 1993, p. 39).

Indian elite can be characterised as a social category that held power over Bourdieu's subfields like academic (discourse), bureaucracy, politics and economy. New studies suggest a colonial legal system, at least since the eighteenth century, which is open-ended and plural in accommodating the indigenous understandings, especially in legislation related to culture and social customs (Benton, 2002, p. 6). At this particular juncture, elites in colonial Malabar played a crucial role in the colonial legislation on the social and customary practices. And these

elites, with whom the British collaborated, were not a particular caste or class cutting across time, but were determined by the capacity of the sections to establish their powers in the public sphere.

Indian Slavery Act V of 1843

The legal restriction on slavery by the proclamation of 1792 is considered as the first legal intervention of the colonial British in the customary practices of the Malabar. Agrestic slaves in Malabar, which were bound by the land for the agricultural purposes were constituted by the castes like *Pulayan*, *Walluvan*, *Parian* and *Cheruman*. The origin of the slavery and how far they were attached to the land is still contentious among academia. It would be correct up to the extent that the slaves had to be bound to the land in such a predominantly agrarian society. This had been practised to ensure the availability of agricultural labour without any interruption and the extraction of the maximum surplus at the minimal cost. Whenever a master is not in a condition to providing subsistence to the slave, then they were permitted to work for another person and as soon as the master's position improved they were obliged to come back (Jayasree, 2012).

However, master never had the absolute power over the slaves. Even though, the master had the power to punish his slave, in the cases of high punishments he had to get the permission from the higher authority. Nature of this higher authority differed according to the region, caste and customs. Sometimes, it might be the powerful *taravads*, (households) sometimes it might be the caste associations, or sometimes it might be the village associations like that of *Naattukkoottam*. Moreover, also the slaves could not send in to the larger distance from his birth/ residential place. These practices were determined by the customary law called *Desachaaram* (Jayasree, 2012, p. 6).

However, the practice of slavery was very much inhuman in Malabar at the time of colonial intervention. Not only untouchability but even 'useability' had been practised there. The Company rule in Bengal had been addressed the slavery and already they had started to take necessary steps to prevent it. Regulation IX and X of Bengal Revenue Consultation on 17th May 1774 had prohibited buying or selling of a slave who is already not such by former legal practice. On 22 July 1789 Governor General Cornwallis declared that those who engaged in the slave trade will be "prosecuted with the utmost rigour in the Supreme Court at the expense of company" (Quoted in Cassels, 2010, p. 178). By 1790, Madras Government also passed the same proclamation on the lines of the Governor General. It was in this context

Malabar came under the control of the British, and the Joint Commissioners who were appointed to look into the condition of Malabar found slavery there. Then in 1793 itself they passed the proclamation against slave traffic and slave trade on the same lines of Bengal and Madras.

The proclamation of the 1793 made no significant influence on the practice of slavery in Malabar. Captain Farmer's letter dated 17th May 1792 on the slave trade in the Malabar Coast noted that the proclamation hardly had any impact. The slaves were extensively traded by the French at Mahe to the islands of Bourbon and Mauritius (Jayasree, 2012, p. 5). In 1793, Joint Commissioners; Jonathan Duncan, Page and Bodam informed to their heads that they had seen the practice of the kidnapping and shipping of slaves and other natives of Malabar even after their proclamation. It was in this context that Government of Madras passed a legislation in 1812, abolishing slave traffic from the province of Malabar. However, this Act was also not at all influential since it made a little effect. MacLeod's letter to principal collector and magistrate of Tanjore asking for preventive measures to check the practice of transporting children by the sea explains the concern for the practices which still exists (Jayasree, 2012).

By 1811, Company Government came up with a proposal for a Felony law on the slavery which made participating in the slave trade as a felony. This act came in to existence on 1st January 1812 and was only applicable to the slave trade by sea. This piece of legislation initiated an extensive debate among the company officials and "became the corner stone of legal debate and actual legislation concerning slavery in India for years to come" (Cassels, 2010, p. 180).

The debate on slavery within the administrative circle sharply belonged to two types of the argument. On the one hand of this debate, were the exponents of the traditionalism, who considered slavery as an integral part of Indian custom both in Hindu and Muhammadan laws and argued against any interference of the government. On the other hand, we had the Evangelicals and the proponents of the utilitarianism, who saw slavery as a major violation of individuality and individual rights and who saw it as the responsibility of colonial administration to civilize the "barbaric" India. Both these camps were very strong and influential during the periods of this debate. We also have another group within the colonial administration who were mostly concerned with the economic interest of Company. Some European officials had given consent to practice slavery for the Company's work. For instance Jonathan Duncan, who was there among the Joint Commissioners on the proclamation of the

abolition of slave trade in Malabar in 1793, and by then the Governor of Bombay, approved the request by the plantation overseer's for the permission to purchase lower caste *Pullalas* as slaves (Cassels, 2010, p. 186). In Malabar, Company had owned slaves on its plantation throughout the late eighteenth and early nineteenth century. Even after the Felony Act there are the company officials who justified and supported the practice of slavery in terms of customs and economic benefit for Company.

This question of the existence of the slavery even after these legislations was noted by the Thomas Hervey Baber a company officials who served in the different department of Malabar. Firstly he was appointed in the revenue department (1798-1808), then he became the district judge of Malabar(1808-1816) and finally appointed as the third circuit judge of the western provincial courts (1816-1824). Being the district judge in Malabar, he found that the practice of the slavery exists even in the plantations by the British. In 1811, he freed one hundred and twenty-three slaves from the plantation of the Murdoch Brown, which was sanctioned by Duncan. This became a point of debate within the colonial administration when Brown challenged his action in the court. For Baber, that opened an arena to fight against slavery, and he submitted his objection to the Foujdari Adawlut on the practice of selling the slaves of revenue defaulters. This court transferred it in to the Governor, and he instructed the Board of Revenue to conduct a study on this issue and submit a report.

Board of Revenue circulated the enquiry among the collectors of Madras Presidency in 1819. Most of the collectors provided a picture of the mutually benefited master-slave relationship as an indigenous custom.¹ Then the board decided not to interfere with the rights of private property claimed by the land owners on the slaves. On 23rd December 1819 Board of Revenue issued an order that prohibited the auctioning of slaves of revenue defaulters. Then Madras Regulation VI of 1829 granted some right to slaves, to prosecute and give evidence as free men in the courts.

Charter of 1833 emancipated slaves in most British possessions. In this line, the evangelicals in India began their cry to pass similar legislation in India. It was in this context that first Law Commission was established in India under the head of a utilitarian T. B

1 Collector Vaughan of Malabar observed that *Cherumas* were in a more comfortable circumstance than any of the lower and poor classes of natives. Collector of Coimbatore remarked that the slaves were better treated by their masters than the common class of free labours. Collector of Trichinopoly argued that emancipating *Pullars* entirely would be ruinous in its consequences both to Revenue and *Pullars*; Collectors answers paraphrased by A.D. Campbell to Hill, Board of Revenue Proceedings 25th November 1819, Parliamentary Papers (1828) XXIV p.899.

Macaulay. This Commission took up the issue of slavery as well. However, they were not concerned about the slave trade but concentrated more on the Masters' rights over the slave. On 1st February 1839 Law Commission submitted a Draft Act, which reduced the masters' rights over the slave. But this act got discouragement from the Governor General Auckland and was returned by the home authority for reconsideration.

Then later on the 27th December 1841 Andrew Amos, the member of the first Criminal Law Commission, prepared a new draft on slavery. This draft, again with further incorporations and corrections published in the Government Gazette on 24th January 1843 This Indian Slavery Act V abolished slavery by making it practices as a criminal offence.

Throughout this process of law making, we see the complete absence of the native voice. All the discussions happened in the colonial administrative sphere, and dictions and the future of the legislation were determined by the power relations within that sphere alone. In the first half of the eighteenth century, there was a tendency to impose the law upon the colonised societies that formulated according to the exclusive western understanding.

The Malabar Marriage Act 1896(Act IV of 1896)

The first attempt at the reformation of the marriage customs among the Nayar community started with the establishment of the Malabar Marriage Association in 1879. This association drafted a bill to legalize *Nayar* marriage and to give a unified code of law for the inheritance of property. On 24th March 1890 C. Sankaran Nayar introduced a bill in the Madras Legislative council. Objectives of the bill were, to legalize *Nayar* marriages by registering *Sambandham*, to make bigamy a punishable offence, to provide legal provision for the divorce and to allow for the restitution of conjugal rights (Thomas, 2002, p. 131). The bill also sought to make husband responsible for the maintenance of the wife and children. The act also supposed to fix the age for marriage as eighteen for men and fourteen for the girls.

Then government formed a commission named as Malabar Marriage Commission in 1891 under T Muthuswami Ayyer as its President. Other members of the committee were Rama Varma Thamburan of Parappanad, Mundappa Bangera, District Munsif of Mangalore, Sir C Sankaran Nayar, H.M Winterbotham and O. Chandu Menon. The aim of this commission was to study the marriage customs of the Hindus in Malabar and to give its opinion on the proposed legislation. They prepared a questionnaire and sent it in to 474 personalities and 332 of it replied. The Commission also collected many local opinions. Finally, they found out

considerable opposition from the *Nambutiri* land lord, head of the *taravads* and even from a section of the educated *Nayars* and a few ladies. Considerable opposition was coming from the northern Malabar where polyandry and the *Sambandham* with *Nambutiri* were quite a few.

Since there had considerable opposition to the proposed act from the different sections of the society, Commission wrote to government in para 59;

We, therefore, do not dispute the view that the proposed legislation is not at present desired by a majority, but we also believe that the uninstructed majority will follow the lead of the enlightened classes and that there need be no apprehension that if the law be framed it will remain a dead letter (Thomas, 2002, p. 134).

When the commission submitted its report, Sankaran Nayar withdrew his earlier bill and presented a new modified bill and this was passed as the Madras Act IV of 1896 or the Malabar Marriage Act of 1896. This act was a diluted version of the earlier bill. It merely recommended the registered *Sambandham* would have the status of the legal marriage. The act was seen as a necessary aid towards the progress and the good morals. The effect of this act was very little since only 57 *Sambandham* were registered between 1897 and 1904 (Chandra Mohan, 1999, p. 464). However, this act was a start kick for the legal intervention in the indigenous customs in a standardizing manner.

There was a transformation in the late eighteenth century in the colonial order of law. Here the constitutional reforms were started because of the various colonial consideration. Natives began to claim their demand using the legislative means, yet it was still in its formative stage. Law making process considered the interest of natives, yet dominated by the colonial rulers.

The Malabar Tenancy Act 1930

The spontaneous and the frequent peasant uprisings in Malabar in the mid nineteenth century got attention from the colonial rulers. The government then appointed T.L Strange as the Special Commissioner to enquire into tenant-land lord relations and to suggest if any further interventions are necessary to place them in a better footings. He rejected the argument of the agrarian discontent and attributed the fanaticism of the Mappilas as the primary cause of the outrages.

In 1880, Government of Madras constituted Malabar Special Commission under the district collector, William Logan. This commission was formed on the basis of an anonymous petition submitted to the government by highlighting the agrarian grievances (Kunhi Krishnan,

1993, p. 19). Thus, Logan was asked to report on the general question of the tenure of the land and of the tenant right in Malabar and alleged insufficiency of the compensation offered by the landlord for the improvement made by the tenants. Logan studied the nature of the land ownership and the land tenure in Malabar. He argued that “British authorities and British courts have never realised the true original state of the relations subsisting between Janmis and other classes interested in the soil” (Malabar Special Commission, 1881-82, Malabar Land Tenures, 1882). For him, *Janmis* and *Kanamdar* were not the absolute owners of the land. He argued that the *Janmam* and *Kanam* were the political office, and right to protect the inhabitance respectively, which evolved historically, and in-turn enjoyed a share of the produce as a return to their services. After his elaborative study, he proposed for the immediate legal intervention to protect the actual tillers of the soil. He proposed that the legislation should provide permanency of tenure for the actual cultivator. He never recommended the granting of the permanent right to the intermediary tenants, on the ground that would lead to the impoverishment of the actual cultivator.

Government forwarded the report of Logan to several experienced officers who had served the regions like Herbert Wigram, A. Macgregor, P.P. Hutchins, W. Huddleston, G.A. Ballard, T. Kunhiraman Nair, and K. Krishan Menon. The net result of the finding of the committee was confusing. Wigram and Macgegor had differed with the findings of the Logan but stated that the legislative reforms are necessary. P.P Hutchins stood close to the opinion of the Logan Where T.K Kunhiraman Nair, opposed any legislative measures. Ballard, Sankaran Nair and Krishana Menon had the opinion that permanency should be given to the *Kanam* tenure, not to the actual cultivators.

Because of these confusing conclusions government then appointed a special commission with T. Madhava Rao as the President and William Logan, Wigram, Sankaran Nayar and Karunakara Menon as the members. All other members except Logan, had already committed to the idea of the permanency of the intermediary tenants and hence, the committee suggested cutting down on the *Janmis* power on 17 July 1884 with the strong dissent of the Logan. However, on 20th July 1885 this proposal was rejected by the Charles Turner, the Chief Justice on the ground that the committee did not consult both the lords and tenants.

Again government constituted a new committee in 1885 on the lights of the criticism. This Master committee was formed by the interest of both the tenures (only intermediary tenures) and *Janmis*. The committee recommended that the best thing with regards to the

agriculture be the least interference by the state. Indeed, the committee was trying to have a compromise between the intermediaries and *Janmis*. It rejected the idea of the legislation to give the permanency of the tenure but suggested a legislation to legalize the payment of compensation for the improvements made by the tenants. By this time, the initial interest on the question of the actual cultivator had given way to the question of the protection of the interest of the intermediary tenants.

On the basis of the recommendation of the committee, The Malabar Compensation for Tenants Improvement Act was introduced in the legislative council on 30th March of 1886 and passed on 28th October 1886 as Act I of 1887. This Act provided that every tenant should be compensated for improvements to be made by him or his predecessors, after getting ejected from his holding. Here the improvements were listed out but the compensations were not fixed. Moreover, this was corrected by the amendment to this Act in 1900.

Again the question of the tenancy reform actively came in to the colonial sphere after the Mappila rebellion. In 1922 M. Krishnan Nayar submitted a tenancy bill to the Madras Legislative Council, which recommended the permanent occupancy right to the intermediaries who hold tenures for 25 years. Now *Janmis* played a tactical role by highlighting the issues of the *Verumpattakkar*, which were not addressed by the Krishnan Nayar's Bill. It was in this context, the very crucial election to the Legislative Council happened in 1923. Tenancy Association could only elect one out of two of their candidates. In 1924, the elected member Krishnan Nayar again submitted a new bill that included the case of the *Verumpattakkar* as well. Leaders of the tenancy movement asked for the support of the Congress members in the Legislative Council to pass this bill and with the help of the Congress leaders it was passed in 2nd September 1926. However, Governor did not give his assent to this Act on the ground that it was against the law.

The tenants disappointed with this situation conducted protest meetings against the British government in the different part of the Malabar.² Then government appointed a committee in 1927 under Diwan Bahadur Raghavayya to report on the question of tenancy legislation Malabar. The leaders of tenants agitation boycotted the committee by saying that the majority of the members were constituted by the supporters of the *Janmis*. Then

2 On 25 November 1926 in Calicut. The following days also witnessed the protest in different parts of Malabar.

government included Krishna Menon in to the committee. By this time in the arena of the national movement also tenancy issue of Malabar became a significant issue and on 1928 Congress organized an All Kerala Tenants Conference, which was presided by Lala Lajpat Rai. Then the tenancy leaders had started an agitation for the dismissal of the Law Member and recall of the Governor. It was the same time, the Law Member C.P. Rama Swami Ayyer's term expired, and M. Krishnan Nayar was appointed as the new Law Member.

It was in this complex situation, the government decided to go with the tenancy legislation and a modified bill was introduced in the Legislative Council on 6th August 1929. It was passed in the October 1929, after getting the opinion of the Select Committee which constituted the prominent personalities including Madhavan Nair and Krishnan Nair. It got the assent of the Governor on 28th March 1930 and finally got the approval of the Viceroy on 1 December 1930.

In the case of tenancy legislation, the discussion was started in the colonial administrative sphere. However, by the late nineteenth century there was an incorporation of the natives into the discussion. By the second decades of the twentieth century, there was the domination of an indigenous middle class in the discourse on reform. Here they could undoubtedly transform the idea of change according to their interest. In the beginning, question was about the tenant-landlord relationship with reference to the actual cultivators. However, by the course of time there was a shift in this paradigm which later became the concern about the intermediary tenants. This change represents the capturing of the public sphere by a newly emerged middle class.

An analysis of these legislations gives a gradual development of the method of law making. Initially, there was only the British in its discourse, later we have the incorporation of the natives with the traditional landlord class held the superior power among the natives. Lastly, we have an emerging middle class from the natives who gradually capture power in the discourse and finally become dominant up to an extent to shift the entire focus of such an initiation. In this process, the class and caste affiliations and interests of the indigenous elites at those particular junctures determined the nature and content of the legislations with social implication.

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